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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is meant to summarise the final results regarding the plasmon analysis based on OAM sorter. The aim is to prove that we can achieve a substantial scientific advancement using the OAM-sorter that was not possible without it.

We document here both the actual scientific results and the partial attempts that could not be brought to conclusions.

The deliverable is separated into 2 main chapters.

Chapter 1 reports the efforts to produce the Q-SORT setup for different kinds of plasmon observation and explains why the setup has to be different for every specific experiment.

Chapter 2 reports the actual scientific results, of high fundamental relevance, that we obtained for volume plasmons. The experimental results are qualitatively and quantitatively compared with simulation.

Conclusions are drawn at the end.

It is worth highlighting here that the OAM sorter allowed us to better understand the characteristics of plasmon loss excitation and to find a new phenomenon consisting of the 'spontaneous Emission' of quanta of OAM in the interaction with plasmon. Surprising theoretical results were also obtained thanks to the definition of coherence through innovative density matrix formalism: we showed that the coherence of the initial OAM state superposition of the electron is partially preserved after the electron-plasmon scattering, which is reflected mathematically by the possibility of expressing the post-scattering electron density matrix as the sum of one fully coherent term containing the initial OAM values and another term which is characterised by full OAM decoherence. The theory was confirmed by experiment in this case as well.

Chapter 1: SETUP AND OPTIMISATION

1.1 Basic setup

The most complex and complete application of the OAM sorter is its use in combination with an EELS spectrometer. The aim, as foreseen by the Project, is to produce an OAM-EELS doubly dispersed spectrum. To this aim we produced the configuration as in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Microscope schemes for the OAM sorter in TITAN HOLO. The two schemes are intended to imaging the S2 (SAD1) plane (up) or the OAM spectrum (down).

The configuration is here represented through our ray-tracing software. The image features two possible configurations where the switch between the imaging and diffraction mode is obtained by a change of the XL between roughly 30% and 50%. In practice the XL lens is the new “diffraction lens” and its value determines to which plane we are looking at [1]. The projection lens excitation has been also controlled in order to have the OAM dispersion orthogonal to the energy dispersion.

This new setup permits us to increase the magnification so that in the OAM direction orthogonal to the energy dispersive direction there is a sufficient magnification so that the OAM spectrum is adequately sampled in terms of number of pixels.

This configuration is fundamentally based on a STEM (i.e. converging) illumination and the typical used convergences are between 1 to 7 mrad.

The upper bound is mainly due to the typical aberrations, the lower is instead a geometrical effect related to the size of the sorter’s electrode.

The focal distance of the objective of this microscope used for our experiment is $f = 3.5$ mm and 2 mrad corresponding to a radius of $R = 7$ μm in the back focal plane of the objective lens. The radius of the convergence corresponds directly to the size of the beam at the entrance of Sorter1 if no sample is present.

Considering that the lateral dimension of the needle constituting the sorter is about $1\mu\text{m}$, this implies that using a convergence below 1 mrad results in major part of the beam to be obstructed by the sorter.

1.2 OAM-EELS spectroscopy at low energy.

The delocalisation and decoherence are potential problems for measuring the OAM spectrum of inelastically scattered electrons.

The inelastic scattering in general is described by the mixed dynamic form factor. An equivalent way to describe its effect is to imagine having the electrons localised in a near-Gaussian wave packet after scattering (see D4.4). The final result will be the incoherent sum of the propagation from such states.

The positioning of the scattered wave is very much dependent on the scattering phenomena we need to analyse: for core-loss phenomena the inelastically generated wavepacket is centred on the atom; for low-loss phenomena (e.g. surface plasmon modes on a particle) the natural “centre” is the centre of the particle [2]. For volume plasmons as here instead there is practically no boundary condition and all points are equivalent.

A rule of thumb estimation of the width of the equivalent scattering centre is given by the minor between the delocalization width $\delta = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi\theta_E}$ and the probe size, where $\theta_E \approx \frac{\Delta E}{E_{TOT}}$ is the characteristic scattering angle and E_{TOT} is the total relativistic energy [3,4].

Substituting for $\Delta E = 1$ eV we find a size of 250nm, whereas the characteristic angle is of the order of 1 μrad .

For such low loss the probe size width for a 1-7 mrad experiment is much smaller than the delocalisation and therefore the angular distribution of low-angle scattering is dominated by the convergence angle of the probe while the inelastic scattering process only produces a minor deviation from this angular distribution.

If we now imagine that the inelastic scattering changes the OAM of the electron beam we can wonder how precisely this is measured by the OAM sorter.

The OAM uncertainty principle for OAM dictates that $\sigma_L \sigma_r > \hbar \Delta r$, namely the uncertainty on the OAM is larger than the ratio between the displacement of the scattering barycentre Δr and the width σ_r of the scattered wavefunction itself.

Let's consider the case of the volume plasmon: every point can be the centre of the inelastically scattered wave. If we now imagine that both the width of the wave after scattering σ_r and its centring Δr are limited mainly by the size of the probe we find, without any further post-selection, that $\sigma_L \approx 1\hbar$

This resolution of $1\hbar$ is appropriate for most applications. In fact an appropriate post processing could be used to trace back the actual contribution from each OAM transitions due to scattering.

If we consider a bound surface plasmon the scattering centre is dictated by the particle position. In the small probe case the electrons interact only with a small part of the plasmon mode. Due to the limited size of the illuminated area it is impossible to determine the symmetry of the plasmon mode as it will always be approximated by the dipole term. A notable exception is given by those points where border effects are very strong. One of such points has been proposed for the identification of very large plasmon dichroism in a recent paper [5]. This kind of measurements will be one of the aims of the application of the sorter in the immediate future.

In the case where the probe is larger than the particle, one would see the modes full symmetry, which is more relevant for modal analysis. Therefore there are applications of the sorter in both low and high convergence setups.

1.3 Detection range post selection

One possible way to improve the OAM resolution is to do an appropriate post selection of the scattering angle. The detail of this will be explained in D4.4 but it is sufficient to say that, by limiting the collection angle of the OAM sorter, we are limiting the linear phase gradient due to off-axis tilt that is disturbing the measurements in favour of the azimuthal phase gradient due to vortex.

We attempted this but with very little success but we document here the steps in this directions.

This could be done in different ways :

- 1) A circular diaphragm in front of sorter 1
- 2) A rectangular aperture in the plane of sorter 2. After the coordinate transformation this is equivalent to the circular aperture as in point 1.

- 3) A rectangular aperture in a plane corresponding to sorter 2 in a different point of the projection system.

Solution 1 was not used as experimentally the aperture was very difficult to centre with the appropriate precision. Moreover it would have not given any flexibility.

Solution 2 is more interesting since it allows to select the desired detection angle: this can be easily done by moving the beam with respect to the slit and by compensating for the beam position adjusting the potential applied to the sorter 2, all while keeping the slit stationary.

The only problem is that sorter 2 like all MEMS is quite delicate, and it turned out to be difficult to attach a ledge or a slit without introducing accidental shorts.

Solution 3 would be in principle preferred but in practice not possible: the only plane where the slit could be inserted in the microscope is the additional SAD plane indicated as SAD2. But in the configuration we are currently using this plane is not conjugated with the sorter 2 plane.

The only possibility to implement this would be to use the standard STEM optical configuration that assures that SAD1 and SAD2 are in conjugated planes. However, in this case the limitations of the standard projection system without the addition of the XL lens, which here would be used only to reimage the SAD1 to the SAD2 planes, would simply produce a very small OAM spectrum. We found that one quanta of OAM would occupy roughly one pixel in the camera of the spectrometer. With the relatively old spectrometer we had so far in TITAN HOLO in Jülich it is not possible to introduce any additional magnification in the OAM direction.

A different possibility would be to abandon the acquisition of the entire OAM-EELS spectrum and rather get only an EFTEM image of the OAM plane including the radial coordinate. In this case the spectrometer would introduce an additional x10 magnification that would help image the OAM spectrum with a sufficient number of pixels.

Finally there could be other ways to improve the magnifications without using the XL lens, for example a far smaller periodicity of Sorter 2 would help create a larger OAM spectrum but this is 1) technically challenging and 2) it would induce an even larger demand for mechanical stability as smaller displacements would more easily affect the functioning of the sorter.

This will be one of the primary development after the end of the Q-SORT project.

1.4 Low-angle setup

The standard setup cannot reach a real low-angle collection of the order of 20-200 μrad . Normally this regime can be reproduced in low-mag mode when the objective lens is off.

Unfortunately when the objective is off the objective aperture is not in the back focal plane of the sample but about in the same plane as the sample. The SAD1 aperture is instead in the focal plane.

One possibility is therefore to use the Sorter 1 in SAD1 and sorter 2 in SAD2. Unfortunately we did not have time to test this configuration.

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Such a scheme is shown in Figure 2 below. However, the focal distance would be of the order of 20 mm that is too small with respect to the 500 mm of the effective focal between S1 and S2 in the “standard” corrector off configuration.

Figure 2 scheme for using the LOWMAG condition for OAM sorting. The sorter elements are in SAD01 and SAD2. This scheme is difficult to use due to the small focal distance between the two.

We therefore considered another possibility, namely working with objective on but putting the sample in the C3 position.

Figure 3 Scheme with the sample in C3.

This configuration is based on c3 off and a small adjustment of condenser minilens (cm), but here free lens control is required.

The angular demagnification factor is roughly $3/130 \approx 1/40$ that would be perfect to get 2mrad in the objective to correspond to 50 μ rad in C3.

From the sample plane downward the propagation is more or less the same of a standard Sorter and this is very useful. We used this configuration in a tentative mode. However, we don't have a way to observe and centre the sample in an easy way.

Chapter 2: Volume plasmon: OAM measurements

What follows is a paper manuscript based on the measurement for volume plasmon. These data are much more interesting than the initial planned studies on nanostructures. We shifted the nanostructuring from the particle to the beam itself and we probe the fundamental nature of electron-plasmon interaction.

We believe these studies are better suited than nanostructure to show the unicity of the OAM-sorter for two reasons: 1) for plasmon mode analysis in particles a competitive experimental

scheme there already exists: scanning the probe in EELS around the nanoparticle. This technique permits to characterise the particle plasmon mode. For the here reported plasmon experiment the result are completely new since there is no method, to our knowledge, to describe the OAM state of the electron after scattering 2) the data here obtained are an initial example of quantum state tomography that allows to describe the full density matrix of electrons after inelastic scattering: a long sought-for experimental method that is strongly simplified by the fact that OAM is a degree of freedom.

Abstract: *Electron vortex beams have attracted a lot of attention for disclosing the control of a quantized degree of freedom for a charged particle like the electron: the orbital angular momentum. With respect to light vortex beam, an electron vortex beam presents a more rich phenomenology: relativistic spin-orbit coupling, charged azimuthal currents and magnetic momenta associated to a beam in vacuum.*

The new OAM sorter device coupled for the first time to an energy loss spectrometer is used here to understand the electron vortex behaviour in interaction with a sea of plasmons. In particular we find that a superposition of vortex beams lose energy and quanta of OAM coiling down to the state to lower OAM as electrons do in an excited atom in an electro-magnetic vacuum. We also find by comparison of theory and experiments that the electron-plasmon interaction still preserves part of the coherence of the electron beam in OAM space.

The dawn of electron beam shaping has put our attention to a forgotten degree of freedom for electrons: the orbital angular momentum or better the projection of the angular momentum vector operator on the main electron propagation. A simple analysis shows that its spatial representation is proportional to the azimuthal gradient of the phase around a chose optical axis.

Since the wavefunction cannot be directly measured this definition is not a direct method to measure the spectrum of this operator. Conversely the newly created electron optical device named “OAM sorter” allows to readily obtain the OAM spectrum on the screen [1].

In this work we tune the electron microscope in a OAM sorter configuration and couple the resulting OAM spectrum with an electron energy spectrometer.

The OAM dispersion is setup orthogonal to the Energy dispersion so we can appreciate in a single image the selection rules of a given transition in the angular basis: something that so far has always been missing.

The simplest EELS experiment is the analysis of volume plasmons. These collective excitations represent the main response of the material to swift electrons and are quite well described by a solution of the Maxwell equation, plasmons are indeed more correctly described as a mixed light and material mode. The main theoretical framework is that of “random phase approximation” but we will not enter in this level of detail.

For this work we considered a simple carbon sample and different kinds of electron probes. We used the calibration cross grating film or a sheet of multiple layer graphene.

Figure 4 Left: Scheme of OAM–EELS setup of the microscope: the OAM and energy dispersion occur in orthogonal directions. Right: Experimental OAM-EELS spectrum of low-loss in Carbon. The OAM and EELS spectra are visible on the two axes.

As a first experiment we illuminated the sample with a $\ell = 0$ featureless illumination. The image shows the full OAM/EELS spectrum. Unfortunately, the OAM spectrum is affected by alignment problems so the OAM resolution is worse than the ideal $\Delta\ell = 1$.

Nevertheless, the image clearly shows that both energy and OAM can be measured in a single scattering event. The interpretation of these double spectra is quite easy. The volume plasmon scattering does not alter significantly the OAM distribution. In mathematical terms of $P(\ell, \Delta E) = O(\ell)S(\Delta E)$ the dependence on OAM and energy loss is factorized as the product of two independent functions.

In fact the OAM spectrum for each energy should be simply a peak around zero while in reality we obtain a more complex spectrum that is only due to the imperfect alignment. Therefore the features are repeated with appropriate scaling for all OAM spectra at each energy loss.

As a demonstration of this factorisation we considered a few 2D spectra and normalised each OAM profile at given energy to its maximum.

Figure 5 Detailed analysis of OAM-EELS spectra like in Fig. 4. The image on the bottom is obtained by the one on top after normalization so that each OAM spectrum for a given energy has an intensity maximum at of 1.

The result is to a good level of approximation the same for every energy. In a second experiment we used a structured beam illumination with 2 kinds of petal beam with $|\ell|=2, 4$. The result is shown in Figure 6 below. In this case the spectra has been deconvolved to account for the PSF of the OAM-sorter.

Figure 6 OAM-EELS spectra of carbon-loss obtained with a petal beam $|l|=4$ (the phase of the hologram is indicated in the inset on the right)

In this case the image seems to give more clearly the impression that there is a blurring in the plasmon loss region. To confirm this we normalized the OAM profiles at different energies. The result is shown in Figure 7 below.

Figure 7 OAM-EELS spectra of low-loss obtained with a petal beam $|l|=4$ (the phase of the hologram is indicated on the right) on a carbon film. The OAM profile at each energy are normalized.

The image clearly shows that the OAM is not completely conserved in the excitation of volume plasmons.

In qualitative terms we can say that the plasmon excitation tends to dump the phase modulation of the electron beam toward the $\ell=0$.

One interesting aspect of this is that if we imagine to post select a value of ℓ in the microscope before any decoherence inside the material we can determine an initial plasmon wave shape. For example if we post select electrons after scattering with $\ell=2$ we can say that we are selecting conditions where the OAM has been transferred to the volume plasmon matrix.

However, the fact that the electron exchanges exactly a single OAM with the plasmon does not mean that the plasmon itself is in a stable vortex condition.

The argument lacks of enough investigation since most of the attention in literature has always been dedicated to surface plasmon polaritons and in particular to their confinement in plasmonic structure [11].

It should be also considered that (as said above) even if a vortex were generated, due to the lack of a specific centre for the vortex the OAM sorter would give a broader OAM spectrum.

Chapter 3: Data analysis by density matrix representation

The standard analysis of the electro state after an inelastic scattering is often carried out using the concept of mixed dynamic form factor (MDFF) that is strictly related to the density matrix representation of the state.

The mixed dynamic form factor (MDFF) of core loss lends itself to an interpretation in terms of the incoherent sum from scattering centres in real space.

The case of volume plasmon excitation is a bit more complex. The MDFF can be written as [4]

$$S(q, q') \propto \frac{\bar{q} \cdot \bar{q}'}{\omega} \delta(\bar{q} - \bar{q}') \quad (1)$$

The presence of the $\delta(\bar{q} - \bar{q}')$ means that the density matrix is now automatically diagonalized in q/q' space.

However, we can leave aside the MDFF approach and re-start from a directly physically meaningful modelling of the effect of plasmons. The scattering can be calculated as a randomisation of the momentum due to scattering. In such a case the probability to be scattered to a state $\langle \psi_{ef} |$ is given by.

$$P(ef) = \int_0^{q_{pmax}} \left| \langle \psi_{ef} | \left\langle f_{k_p} \right| V | i \rangle \right| \left| \psi_{ei} \right\rangle \right|^2 dk_p \quad (2)$$

where ψ_{ef} is the state we project to ψ_{ei} is the probe and $|i\rangle$ and $|f\rangle$ are the initial and final plasmon state. Our initial state is the plasmon vacuum $|0\rangle$ and final state is $|f\rangle = a^\dagger_{k_p}|0\rangle$ with a and a^\dagger being the ladder operator for the plasmon.

As a simplification we assume here a point-like potential $V = \delta(r_e - r_p)$ while more correctly we should consider a propagator between the swift electrons and the plasmon generation¹. This simply means that we can write

$$P(ef) = \int_0^{|q| < q_{pmax}} |\langle \psi_{ef} | \exp(i\bar{q}\bar{r}_e) | \psi_{ei} \rangle|^2 \delta(\bar{q} - \bar{k}_p) d\bar{k}_p \quad (3)$$

Where $\bar{q} = \bar{k}_f - \bar{k}_0 = \bar{k}_p$. The integral is therefore a convolution in momentum space.

This means that to obtain the intensity in a given representation we must sum incoherently over different intensity distributions in the desired representation where the initial wave has been shifted by an amount k_p .

In the momentum space this simply means to get the original diffraction and blur it by a plasmon distribution of exchanged momenta that, for simplicity, we can initially assume to be a Gaussian with width the most likely momentum exchange.

According to theory [4] the most likely momentum is simply $k_{pmp} = \frac{2\pi\theta_E}{\lambda}$

In the position representation, to the present level of approximation, the scattering is contained in the phase $\exp(i\bar{q}\bar{r}_e)$. In practice the plasmon have the effect to “randomize” the momentum distribution of the probe. The randomization approach, a sort of “frozen phonon” [6] version of the scattering does not take into account the fact that the plasmons are generated by the electron beam and of the initial population of the plasmon state. In the case of plasmon there is not a thermal population so the effect of the beam is the only effect.

In the OAM representation the calculation is more cumbersome because it requires the use of a “Montecarlo”-like approach, whereas of course there are also complex analytical approaches.

3.1 Numerical calculation and density matrix representation for the OAM state

In order to evaluate the effect of the scattering we considered a series of tilted beams representing different scattering trajectories with momentum k_p . For each condition we calculated the OAM spectrum.

$$P(ef) = \int_0^{|q| < q_{pmax}} |\langle \ell, |k_f| | \exp(i\bar{q}\bar{r}_e) | i \rangle | \psi_{ei} \rangle|^2 d\bar{k}_p \quad (4)$$

The incoherent sum of the OAM spectral intensities produces the simulated spectrum to be compared with experiments.

Moreover we can explicitly calculate the density matrix.

¹ Such propagator is responsible for the modified Bessel function potential appearing in electron matter interaction (see ref. 10)

$$\rho_{\ell\ell'} = \int_0^{|k| < k_{pmax}} \langle \ell | \exp(-i\bar{q}\bar{r}_e) | \psi_{ei} \rangle \langle \psi_{ei} | \exp(i\bar{q}\bar{r}_e) | \ell' \rangle d\bar{k}_p \quad (5)$$

Here in agreement with eq.1 we assumed that $\bar{q}' = \bar{q}$ that the plasmon effect is the same. It is easy to deduce the formula by summing the density matrices corresponding to each \bar{k}_p scattering and assuming each of this state as a pure state.

Figure 8 Density matrix in the OAM representation (up) for different amounts of coupling with plasmon scattering: the diagonal corresponds to the OAM spectrum (bottom) For a pure petal beam there are only the diagonal +/-4 terms and their anti-diagonal. A perfectly diagonal matrix would correspond to a complete loss of coherence.

In practice we calculate the wave function for each value of k_p and convert each pure state that derives from this into its density matrix representation. The density matrices are then summed together. The diagonal term still represents the OAM spectrum, but now we have a better idea of the coherence.

The relevant factor here is the ratio between the maximal displacement and the convergence angle. The 3 curves correspond to displacement of 2,4,6 times the semi-convergence.

The OAM spectra for the 3 different size of the displacement are also displayed indicating that for increasing momentum exchange the two lateral peaks tend to broaden while a peak at the centre for $\ell=0$ increases progressively.

This idea is consistent with the OAM EELS spectrum that indicates an increase of the 0 and low OAM contribution with increase of the energy loss that is clearly related to the increase of the exchanged momentum.

3.2 Coherence estimation

Given the density matrix in OAM representation and neglecting radial effects we can write the density matrix as [7,8]

$$\rho = \sum a_{m,m'} |m\rangle\langle m'| \quad (6)$$

where a should not be confused with the above ladder operator. The OAM spectrum gives only the diagonal elements of the density matrix, but in order to understand better the effect of the plasmon scattering we must evaluate also the coherence off-diagonal terms in the density matrix. We need to choose another basis and in particular the real space representation.

The diagonal term gives

$$\langle \bar{r} | \rho | \bar{r} \rangle = \sum_{m,m'} a_{m,m'} \exp(i(m - m')\theta) \quad (7)$$

If we limit the available OAM to the cases where $m=4$ and -4 and 0 , even of the 0 component was not in the probe.

Then for the non-zero coefficients we find that

$$\langle \bar{r} | \rho | \bar{r} \rangle = 2\text{Im}(a_{4,-4}) \sin(2m\theta) + a_{-4,-4} + a_{4,4} = 2\text{Im}(a_{4,-4}) \sin(2m\theta) + 2a_{4,4} \quad (8)$$

If we assume a 4,-4 symmetry of all coefficients and neglect a phase shift the equation simply writes as

$$\langle \bar{r} | \rho | \bar{r} \rangle = 2\text{Im}(a_{4,-4}) \sin(2m\theta) + [2a_{4,4} + a_{0,0}] + 4\text{Im}(a_{4,0}) \sin(m\theta) \quad (9)$$

The off-diagonal term is responsible for the modulation in real space. For a pure state case with a perfect petal beam $|a_{4,-4}| = |a_{4,4}|$ while for a completely incoherent case $|a_{4,-4}| = 0$.

However if we observe the density matrices for the decoherence mechanism described above we find $|a_{4,-4}| = |a_{4,4}|$. As said the momentum exchange that we simulated produces a broadening of the diagonal terms outside ± 4 and an increase in particular of the term $a_{0,0}$. $a_{0,0}$ is an incoherent base-line of electrons that have undergone a scattering. The effect of such a scattering is to reduce and simplify the phase structure.

The persistence of the off-diagonal terms $a_{4,-4}$ is a very interesting result. The linear momentum exchange cannot alter the phase relation between the positive and negative OAM part of the petal beam. This indeed can only be altered by a rotation that is never possible with a simple shift.

To verify the presence of the off-diagonal terms in experiments we cannot use the OAM spectrum alone but we need a different representation, in particular the space representation available at the diffraction of sorter 1.

The experimental images for the beam are visible in the figure below.

Figure 9 Experimental unwrapped image of the petal beam with zero-loss and plasmon loss electrons

Figure 10 simulated unwrapped image of the petal beam with 0-loss and carbon loss electrons. The latter is here obtained with 2 simulation methods i.e. by Montecarlo (centre) and the Gaussian blurring of the probe followed by unwrapping(right).

The two experimental images depict the unwrapped beam in the case of zero loss and 20 eV energy loss. The zero loss image shows a perfectly defined contrast. Clearly we have more than two frequencies and this is an artefact of diffractive electron optics (beyond the geometric approximation) but the interference almost vanishes in the dark parts. On the contrary in the image formed with inelastically scattered electrons the details are affected by a blurring. This is visible also in the loss of contrast of most of the features.

This work could be the basis for a complete quantum state tomography (QST) of the electrons state after interaction. QST would be particularly favourable due to the discrete nature of the OAM.

We propose here a simpler approach to combine the information arising from spectra in figure 8 and unwrapped images in figure 9.

A very rough estimation of the $a_{4,-4}$ term can be derived by looking at the ratio $C = \sigma/I_{med}$ between the intensity peak to valley variation and its average. We find it varies from 0.9-1 in the elastic case and roughly 0.7-0.8 in the inelastic case. In the rough hypothesis that the $a_{4,-4}$ is the main source of fringe contrast, we find

$$C \approx \frac{2a_{4,-4}}{2a_{4,4}+a_{0,0}} \quad (10)$$

From the OAM spectra we calculated that $a_{0,0}$ varies between 20% in the elastic case (due to imperfection of the hologram) to roughly 50% due to inelastic effects. This is still roughly consistent with the assumption that $|a_{4,-4}| = |a_{4,4}|$ in both cases but better calculation should account also for the broadening and redistribution of the OAM to other channels.

3.3 Data interpretation

Vortex beams have been a large surprise for their counterintuitive nature of charged current that appear to have a rotation but still do not present any emission. This is always explained reconsidering that in vacuum a beam without external forces should not radiate because otherwise the energy and momentum would not be conserved at the same time [9,10].

However, in a material this is not true anymore, and we have a mechanism of plasmon emission that is asymmetric with a higher probability of losing quanta of OAM than gaining them. Plasmons are surely produced both by flat and structured beams but we can reinterpret the loss/gain of quanta of OAM as a sort of spontaneous emission.

In fact if we consider the electron state with well-defined initial and final OAM state and express everything in terms of the azimuthal coordinates the transition potential for the electron is

$$V = \exp(i|k_p r| \cos(\theta)) \quad (11)$$

This means that we can formally write the emission/absorption of quanta as $V = \sum_m J_m(|k_p r|) \exp(im\theta)$, J_m being the Bessel function of order m. since every $\exp(i\theta)$ corresponds to a change of quanta of OAM we can use an analogy with the PINEM-EELS emission/absorption.

The spatially averaged coupling $\beta \approx |k_p \sigma_r|$ where σ_r is the extent of the probed area is here related to the amount of energy loss considered.

$$V = \sum_m J_m(|k_p r|) (b^{\dagger m} + b^m) \quad (12)$$

where b^\dagger, b are the ladder operators for the electron OAM.

Note that the both single or multiple quanta transfer of OAM are related to a single plasmon emission.

A modification to this formula could allow us to explain the apparently missing effect in explaining experiments, namely the asymmetry between increase and decrease of the OAM. In

fact the experimental case the $\ell=0$ beam that does not get any change of the OAM and the petal beam $\ell=\pm 4$ that mainly produce lower values of OAM could indicate that there is a sort of “spontaneous emission” effect.

Probably the best way to account for this is to consider the plasmon + electron system

$$V_{TOT} = \sum_m J_m(|k_p r|)(b^{\dagger m} c^m + b^m c^{\dagger m}) \quad (13)$$

with m only positive and c are the ladder operators for the plasmon OAM. So that when the Fermi rules is written explicitly

$$P = |\langle n'_p \ell'_e | V | n_p \ell_e \rangle|^2 \quad (14)$$

the lack of OAM in the plasmon population leads to the following selection rules

$$\langle n'_p \ell'_e | b^{\dagger} c | n_p = 0, \ell_e \rangle = 0 \text{ always, and}$$

$$\langle n_p + 1, \ell_e - 1 | b c^{\dagger} | n_p = 0, \ell_e \rangle \approx \ell_e \quad (15)$$

The OAM of the electron ℓ_e can only be lost and the loss is possible only if the values is not zero.

Notice that $\ell = 0$ turns out to have a preferential role because this is the standard condition of the volume plasmon “vacuum” that has naturally no OAM. If the plasmon state were populated with different states we would be able to populate larger OAM states and have OAM absorption as indeed observed in a PINEM experiment with surface plasmon. Such PINEM experiment is also among the collateral results of QSORT [11].

Finally, it is worth noticing that the coupling term β depends on the momentum and therefore the energy of the plasmon. This is consistent with the observation in Fig 7 that the exchange of OAM to plasmon increases with the energy loss.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work we have obtained for the first time a quantum characterisation of the coupling between a plasmon state and an electron vortex beam. The data show the advantage and unicity of the OAM sorter since no other experiment would directly allow the measurement of the OAM spectrum.

The data show the residual post interaction coherence of the electron beam in the OAM basis through a density matrix representation that is particularly well suited for OAM discrete degree of freedom. The data also show the decoherence effects that can be described by analogy with the spontaneous emission of photon in atoms. To do this we carried out a basic scheme of quantum tomography that compares the results in two basis representation. This scheme could be further improved in future.

The paper poses new fundamental questions: the post-selection of the electron OAM state could even in principle point toward a method to create volume plasmons in form of vortices

whereas of course their stability is yet to be established and remains an open question for future studies.

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ANNEX 1: Referee

Referee 1

This is a very interesting work and I can see that it contains a ready paper. I am wondering if it is strictly necessary to use the second quantisation approach toward the end of the theoretical treatment.

We have the impression that it is otherwise difficult to handle the dependence on the population of plasmon this approach has also been used in ref 4.

Do you think it will be possible to measure the correlation of Plasmon and electron OAM?

The lifetime of a volume plasmon is very small and it is even smaller if we consider the fact that they propagate in the direction where the sample is very thin. We can imagine an experiment where volume plasmons are coherently converted into something that can be directly measured.

Referee2

Very interesting work . Do you have more data with different conditions?

Thanks for the question. I just want to mention these data obtained for the logarithmic Spirals used in WP5. These are states that are mapped into dots by the OAM sorter. The images here show the original hologram and the effect of the scattering on the carbon sample.

Differently from the experiment above the OAM-Pr spectra are here obtained by EFTEM at the zero loss (center) and plasmon loss(right). The plasmon loss indicates a broadening of the OAM spectrum in the direction of lower OAM but also of lower logarithmic radial momentum. A larger value of the background is also visible

I suggested you a couple of correction of typos

Thanks corrected.

I find very interesting the connection to the work of McMorran. Do you think you can also emit propagating light in the process?

That is a very interesting question. In principle if there is a deceleration there is also a photon emission but the plasmon is also by itself an electromagnetic mode. It would be also difficult to distinguish it from transition radiation Cherenkov and other low loss processes.

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics - IT	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Inst	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL

Q-SORT

Deliverable D4.3

Manuscript for paper on OAM Sorter characterisation of plasmons